

INFLUENCE OF TRANSVERSE TENSION ON THE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CARBON REINFORCED CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

Textile CFRP (carbon fibre reinforced polymer) reinforcement enables the construction of thin-walled structures such as double-curved shell structures or girder webs with minimal concrete cover due to their insensitivity to corrosion. In contrast to the tensile and flexural behaviour, the capacity of the compression strut of the thin-walled carbon reinforced concrete (CRC) specimens and the influence of transverse tensile loading has not yet been investigated in detail. For steel reinforced concrete components, extensive research has shown a significant reduction of concrete compressive strength as a function of the principal tensile stress. For CRC a different behaviour under biaxial loading is expected compared to steel reinforced concrete. Therefore, the influence of transverse tension on the compressive behaviour of carbon reinforced concrete was investigated at the Institute of Structural Concrete (IMB) of RWTH Aachen University. This paper presents a literature review on the compressive strength of CRC and conventional test setups used to quantify the influence of transverse tension on the compressive strength of steel reinforced concrete. Based on these findings, a new test setup for the investigation of combined compressive and transverse tensile loading in CRC and first test results are presented.

KEYWORDS

carbon reinforced concrete; compressive strength; biaxial loading; compression softening

INTRODUCTION

Carbon reinforced concrete (CRC) structures with textile carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) reinforcement are characterised by high compressive and tensile strength and have great potential for use in thin-walled structures such as double-curved shell structures or webs of beams that are predominantly subjected to in-plane compressive forces, in order to design lightweight, high-performance and durable structures with a minimum material use for sustainable structures (Beckmann et al., 2021). For such structures, an adequate prediction of the capacity of the concrete strut is crucial. In particular, specimens with thin webs, high shear reinforcement ratios or with flat stress field angles are prone to strut failure. Understanding the structural behaviour of CRC under combined compressive and transverse tensile loading is essential as there will be a reduction of strength compared to the uniaxial compressive strength. For steel reinforced concrete structures, extensive research using for example panel tests on reinforced concrete specimens has shown a significant reduction of the concrete compressive strength as a function of the principal tensile stress up to half of the uniaxial compressive strength. In contrast to steel reinforced concrete, the stress transfer mechanisms in carbon reinforced concrete under multi-axial loading remain largely unexplored. Due to the different bond properties of the textile CFRP reinforcement compared to steel reinforcement, the reduced crack spacing and the tendency of the concrete for in-plane cracking, a different behaviour under biaxial loading is expected compared to steel reinforced concrete. Therefore, the experimental investigation of the capacity of the compression strut is essential. As the influence of transverse tension on the compressive strength of CRC has not been investigated in detail, systematic test series using a new test setup and refined measurement techniques were carried out and the first results are presented in this paper.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The presence of textile CFRP reinforcement, which is sensitive to lateral pressure (Stark, Classen, & Hegger, 2019), affects the compressive strength of concrete in general. For non-impregnated textile reinforcement, the yarns are considered as voids that weaken the concrete cross-section (MOLTER, 2005), (VOSS, 2008). The presence of yarns disturbs the load transfer of compressive stresses, resulting in transverse tensile stresses. Both the weft and warp direction of typical biaxial grids form artificial discontinuities (Bielak, 2021). However, this type of disturbance increases as the number of layers increases and the thickness of the concrete between the yarns decreases (Bochmann, 2019). In an extreme case, the concrete acts as two separate discs. This separation can lead to premature failure of the concrete lamella due to second order deformations as the effective thickness is reduced. For CRC with impregnated yarns, extensive research has been carried out by BOCHMANN to investigate the behaviour under uniaxial compression (Bochmann, 2019; Bochmann, Curbach, & Jesse, 2018). He investigated the phenomenon of the reduction of compressive strength for textile reinforced cubic CRC specimens (40 mm edge length) with different reinforcement inclinations in relation to the direction of compressive forces and different manufacturing methods, as well as impregnation materials of the reinforcement (styrene-butadiene (SBR) and epoxy resin (EP), respectively). BOCHMANN proposed a reduction of compressive strength as a function of the reinforcement ratio and the angle of the stress field to the plane of the reinforcement. In his test, he found that EP-impregnated grids have a significantly smaller reduction of compressive strength than SBR-impregnated grids due to the higher transverse stiffness of the resin (Reichenbach, Preinstorfer, Hammerl, & Kromoser, 2021). In addition, the reduction is more pronounced for laminated specimens due to the interlaminar joint in the reinforcement plane resulting in premature failure. Similar results were found by BIELAK in (Bielak & Hegger, 2018) for CRC cubes with EP impregnated grids. According to MOCCIA ET AL. (Moccia, Yu, Fernández Ruiz, & Muttoni, 2021), the casting position also affects the compressive strength of reinforced concrete due to voids under the reinforcement bars resulting from bleeding and plastic settlement of the fresh concrete. For example, for webs in thin CRC girders, these voids may occur below the longitudinal yarns. However, due to the orientations of the yarns in webs of girders, only small voids may occur. In the compression zone of small flanges these voids may be more significant due to the orientation of the yarns. In addition, the formation of voids is dependent on the concrete slump and compaction quality of the concrete.

The compressive capacity of high strength concrete (HSC), commonly used for CRC, under biaxial loading is highly dependent on the transverse load applied (Curbach, Scheerer, Speck, & Hampel, 2011). The reduction of strength for biaxial compression-tension of HSC is even more pronounced than for normal strength concrete (e.g., (Kupfer, 1973)). For HSC subjected to biaxial compression, an increased load-bearing capacity is obtained (Curbach et al., 2011). For CRC specimens, biaxial compression tests with soft-impregnated grids and HSC with a maximum aggregate size of 1 mm were recently performed by BETZ (Betz, 2022). These tests showed a reduction of compressive strength for a lateral pressure that was greater than 50% of the uniaxial prismatic compressive strength. No significant reduction of compressive strength was observed at lower lateral pressures. The utilized CFRP grids act as a cross-sectional weakening, causing the specimens to fail prematurely by splitting in the reinforcement plane. For higher reinforcement ratios and laminated specimens, this effect was more pronounced. It was also found that higher reinforcement ratios resulted in lower compressive stiffness of the CRC specimens.

As in steel reinforced concrete, the capacity of the compression struts cannot be described solely by the uniaxial strength, since additional transverse tensile stresses are induced, for example, by the longitudinal and transverse force reinforcement. These further reduce the effective compressive strength in cracked concrete. This behaviour is well known for steel reinforced concrete and is referred to as compression softening. Transverse tensile stresses weaken the concrete and reduce its compressive strength (Figure 1 a).

Figure 1: Compression softening of reinforced concrete following (Feng, Wu, & Lu, 2018) (a) and exemplary constitutive laws for compression softening in steel reinforced concrete (b)

In general, two different test setups have been used by researchers in the past to investigate compression softening: panel tester (e.g. (Bhide & Collins, 1989), (Vecchio & Collins, 1982), (Belarbi & Hsu, 1991), (Gehri, Mata-Falcón, & Kaufmann, 2022)) and biaxial compression – transverse tension tests on reinforced panels (e.g., (Robinson & Demorieux, 1968), (Schlaich & Schäfer, 1983), (Eibl & Neuroth, 1988), (Kollegger & Mehlhorn, 1990), (Fehling, Leutbecher, Röder, & Stürwald, 2008)). In these tests, for example steel reinforced specimens were loaded in compression in one direction while transvers tension was applied (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Test setups for investigating the influence of transverse tension on the compressive behaviour: panel tests according to (Belarbi & Hsu, 1991) (a) and biaxial compression – transverse tension tests on reinforced panels according to (Fehling, Leutbecher, & Röder, 2009) (b)

In addition to the different test setups, different load controls were applied in the various test series. While for example, in (Belarbi & Hsu, 1991) and (Fehling et al., 2008) sequential loading was also applied, where a defined tensile strain was first applied to the reinforcement and then the compression force was applied while keeping the tension constant during the test, e.g., SCHLAICH & SCHÄFER (Schlaich & Schäfer, 1983) only applied proportional loading, where tension and compression were increased simultaneously. Differences between the test series can be found also in the sequential load control. In contrast to (Fehling et al., 2008), in (Eibl & Neuroth, 1988) the tensile strain in the

investigated specimen was kept constant during the compression loading process instead of keeping the tensile force constant. In the test campaigns by (Bhide & Collins, 1989), pure shear was applied.

The constitutive laws proposed by the researchers to account for compression softening vary strongly (Figure 1 b). While SCHLAICH & SCHÄFER proposed a constant reduction of strength to 80% of the cylindrical compressive strength $f_{c,cyl}$ for transverse tensile strains ε_1 up to 6‰ (no experimental results are available for higher strains), (Vecchio & Collins, 1982) and (Belarbi & Hsu, 1991) suggest exponential reductions as a function of the tensile strain. In (Fehling et al., 2008) a trilinear law is proposed instead. Here, a reduction to $0.75 \cdot f_{c,cyl}$ is chosen for tensile strains up to 2 ‰ and $0.5 \cdot f_{c,cyl}$ (for $f_{ck} = 40$ MPa) for yielding of steel with strains higher than 6 ‰, with linear interpolation in between. In the new generation of Eurocode 2 (CEN/TC 250/SC 2/WG 1, 2021) the influence of the longitudinal tensile strain in mid-depth of the stress-field ε_x as well as the inclination of compression strut θ is included in the reduction of the compressive capacity.

Such extensive experimental investigations have not yet been carried out for components with non-metallic reinforcement. In tests on textile reinforced concrete (TRC) panels with non-impregnated alkali resistant glass fibres in (Hegger & Voss, 2004), (Voss, 2008) it was found that a simple transfer of the panel-testing method is challenging for thin-walled TRC because of stability problems and issues with the load introduction. However, tests have also been carried out in a panel tester for steel reinforced concrete components strengthened with FRP sheets (Zomorodian, 2015). In these studies, the results of (Belarbi & Hsu, 1991) were confirmed, but with reduced softening behavior due to the applied FRP sheets. VOSS proposed a large reduction of compression strut capacity of 29,7 % for non-impregnated textile reinforcement (Voss, 2008), which was recalculated based on the results of his flexural shear tests with strut failure, taking into account the reduction of compressive strength due to the presence of non-metallic reinforcement and transverse tension. For specimens with impregnated textile reinforcement, the influence of transverse tension on the compressive strength has not been systematically investigated yet. The higher ultimate strains and stresses in the CFRP reinforcement may result in higher tensile stresses in the surrounding concrete compared to steel reinforcement. In addition, longitudinal cracks resulting from bond stresses of the reinforcement could split the compression struts and induce spalling of the concrete (Bielak, 2021). BIELAK ET AL. found in large-scale bending tests on CRC I-beams with textile CFRP shear reinforcement that the capacity of the compression strut is further reduced compared to steel reinforced concrete (Bielak, Schmidt, Hegger, & Jesse, 2020). In his specimens, four layers of epoxy impregnated CFRP grids were assembled into the 5 cm thick web. The significantly reduced concrete cover and high shear reinforcement ratio cause premature bond failure and in-plane cracking.

MATERIALS

Concrete

Based on the literature review, uniaxial compression and biaxial compression-tension test were performed. A high-strength, self-compacting concrete (C3-HF2-165-4) was used for all specimens, which is an adaption of the concrete from (Schneider, Butler, & Mechtcherine, 2017) and has also been used, for example in (Bielak, 2021) and (Bielak, 2023). The concrete mixture is given in Table 1. After concreting, the test specimens were left in the formwork for one day and then wrapped in moist jute fabric for seven days to prevent cracking due to shrinkage. They were then stored at 20°C and 65% RH until the day of testing. The compressive strength of cubes (150 x 150 x 150 mm³) and cylinders (d/h = 150/300 mm) according to (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., 2019) and the Young's modulus according to (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., 2021) were determined for the tests on the day of testing. In addition, the compressive strength and flexural tensile strength were determined on prisms (40 x 40 x 160 mm³) according to (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., 2016). The properties of the concrete on the day of testing are given later in the presentation of the test results.

Table 1: Composition of used concrete

Ingredient	Density	Content
	[kg/m ³]	[kg/m ³]
Cementitious binder compound BMC CEM II/C-M Deuna	2962	707
Water	1000	165
Fine quartz sand F38 S	2650	294
Quartz sand 0.1–0.5 mm	2650	243.2
Quartz sand 0.5–1.0 mm	2650	201.4
Quartz sand 1.0–2.0 mm	2650	148.9
Quartz fine gravel 2.0–4.0 mm	2650	593.5
Superplasticizer (polycarboxylatether-basis) MC-VP-16–0205-02	1070	15

CFRP grid

For all specimens, a symmetrical biaxial planar CFRP grid with a yarn spacing of 38 mm in both directions and epoxy impregnation was used. Tensile tests according to (Deutscher Ausschuss für Stahlbeton, 2022) were performed on the yarns in warp and weft direction to characterise the tensile strength and the Young's modulus. Table 2 shows the mean values obtained from $n = 3$ tests each. For the tests carried out on the CRC panels conducted, the weft yarns were oriented perpendicular to compression load.

Table 2: Material properties of CFRP grid

Material [-]	Cross-section*		Axial spacing of yarns		Tensile strength		Young's Modulus	
	[mm ² /m]		[mm]		[MPa]		[GPa]	
	0°	90°	0°	90°	0°	90°	0°	90°
CFRP	95	95	38	38	3710	3490	231	244

* pure fibre cross-section without epoxy impregnation, 3,62 mm² per yarn

NEW TEST SETUP FOR COMPRESSION-TENSION TESTS

Test setup and specimens

A novel test setup has been developed for the investigation of compression softening in carbon reinforced concrete. A combined compression - transverse tension test setup was designed to investigate the compression softening behaviour of slender CRC panels (height h / thickness $t > 2$) following the test setups of e.g., (Schlaich & Schäfer, 1983), (Kollegger & Mehlhorn, 1990), (Fehling et al., 2008) (Figure 3 a).

Figure 3: Test setup for investigation of compression softening in CRC (a) and influence of different load application systems according to (Zilch & Zehetmaier, 2010) (b)

For the application of tensile forces a rigid frame was installed in which the tensile force is applied to the centre of the test specimen via steel bolts, similar to the test setup in (Becks, Bielak, & Hegger, 2021), (Bielak, 2021). Thus, the reinforcement does not need to be clamped and lateral pressure can be avoided. The test specimens were segmented into a central part, containing the test area, and two outer parts for transferring axial tension. The three parts are only connected by reinforcement and the concrete separated by PE sheets to prevent the transfer of compressive stresses between these areas.

Vertical and axial loads are controlled by two different hydraulic cylinders, allowing various combinations of tension (T) and compression (C) loads to be applied. For the application of compression, brush bearing platens were used in accordance to (Kupfer, Hilsdorf, & Ruesch, 1969), (Curbach et al., 2011), in order to minimize the transverse constraint that occurs when using load application via rigid steel platens (Gerstle et al., 1980) (Figure 3 b). A movable calotte was placed on the frame of the upper brush bearing platens to reduce the influence of eccentricities (Bochmann, 2019). The top and bottom of the test specimens were additionally abraded prior to testing to achieve ideal uniform application of compressive load. An accuracy of $\leq 2.5\%$ measured with a sliding calliper was realized, thus meeting the requirements of (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., 2012).

Test series

For the test series, small panels with two layers of textile CFRP reinforcement and a distance between the reinforcement centroid and the specimen edge of $d_1 = 10$ mm were selected. The dimensions of the test area were $300 \times 40 \times 145$ mm³ (Figure 4). The length was chosen to allow for sufficient cracking due to the transverse tensile force while keeping the dimensions as small as possible. Both anchorage parts had a thicker cross section (140×145 mm²) and additional reinforcement layers to prevent premature failure in these areas.

Figure 4: Specimen dimensions and reinforcement layout of uniaxial compression tests (a) and biaxial compression-tension tests (b)

In addition, reference tests were carried out with the dimensions of the test area in the biaxial tests in order to investigate the influence of the specimen dimensions and the brush bearing platens, as well as the influence of CFRP reinforcement on the compressive behaviour. Nine panels were tested in uniaxial compression and four panels were tested with biaxial loading. For the biaxial tests, a proportional application of tensile and compressive forces was chosen while varying the maximum tensile strain. While the compressive forces were applied strain-controlled with a constant ratio of $2 \mu\text{m/s}$ following (Bochmann, 2019), the tensile forces were applied force-controlled with varying ratios to achieve

different maximum tensile strains at compression failure of the specimens. An overview of the test series and the parameters is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Main parameters of the test series

Test series [-]	loading [-]	d_1 [mm]	ρ [%]	grid orientation [mm]
1	uniaxial compression	-	-	-
2	uniaxial compression via steel platens	-	-	-
3	uniaxial compression	10	0.5	0°/90°
4	compression-tension proportional	10	0.5	0°/90°

d_1 : distance between reinforcement centroid and specimen edge; ρ : geometrical reinforcement ratio; 0°/90°: yarns orientated in the direction of applied loads

Instrumentation

In all tests, the deformation was measured in the test area of the specimens using digital image correlation (DIC) from one side and conventional vertical and horizontal linear variable differential transformers (LVDTs) attached to the opposite side of the specimen. Horizontal deformations are measured using two LVDTs, while vertical deformation was measured using three distributed LVDTs. In addition, fibre optic sensors (FOS) were attached to all horizontal yarns in the test area of the biaxial tests with cyanoacrylate adhesive according to (Becks, Bielak, Camps, & Hegger, 2021) to measure the yarn strain continuously. The locations of the LVDTs, DIC and FOS are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Instrumentation for tests series 1-3 (a) and series 4 (b): LVDTs on back side, DIC on front side of specimens and FOS on longitudinal yarns under investigation

TEST RESULTS

Uniaxial compressive strength

In contrast to the tests in (Bochmann, 2019), slender panels ($h/t = 3.6$) were investigated, which might exhibit a different behaviour compared to the small cubes investigated by BOCHMANN. Therefore, in a first step, the uniaxial compressive behaviour was investigated and compared to the compressive strength determined with cylinders ($d/h = 150/300$ mm) according to (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V., 2019), whose strength is usually used for design in Europe (European Standard, 2014). In addition, the influence of the load application system was investigated with a test series using conventional steel platens for compressive loading. Afterwards, the influence of the CFRP grids on the compressive strength of the panels was studied. Figure 6 a) shows the mean uniaxial compressive strengths determined in the test series 1-3. All specimens were produced on the same day and tested after a sufficient time of hardening of at least 40 days. The panel strength determined with steel platens is identical to the cylindrical compressive strength. The use of the brush bearing platens provides a lower compressive strength. As illustrated in Figure 6 b), the fracture patterns are also significantly different for the specimens loaded by steel platens (top) and brush bearing platen (centre) due to the flexibility of the small steel brushes and the resulting reduced lateral restraint which allows individual uniform concrete lamellae to form.

Figure 6: Influence of specimen geometry and CFRP grid on the uniaxial compressive strength (a) and fracture patterns of investigated specimens (b)

For the specimens with two layers of CFRP grid loaded with brush bearing platens, a further reduction of strength can be observed due to the disturbance of the stress flow and the induced transverse tensile stresses caused by the yarns. The failure of these specimens is characterised by delamination of the concrete cover as shown in Figure 6 b (bottom). However, the formation of individual lamellae in horizontal direction is largely prevented by the grids.

Biaxial compression-tension tests

Based on the results described above, the biaxial compression-tension tests with proportional loading were performed to investigate the influence of transverse tension on the compressive strength. Table 4 summarizes the main results of test series 4.

Table 4: Test results of series 4 with proportional biaxial loading

Specimen	$f_{c,cyl}$ [MPa]	F_{max} [kN]	$\sigma_{c2,max}^1$ [MPa]	$\varepsilon_{1,max}^2$ [%]	failure [-]
4-1	93.5	891	74.2	1.8	compression
4-2	93.5	827	68.9	3.9	compression
4-3	93.5	696	58.0	5.3	compression
4-4	93.5	609	50.8	6.0	premature anchorage

¹ calculated using the exact dimensions measured with sliding gauge;

² average panel strains evaluated using DIC

All specimens except of specimen 4-4 failed in compression as intended. Due to poorer than expected bond properties of the grid used, specimen 4-4 showed premature anchorage failure. To prevent this type of failure, larger anchorage areas were chosen for the other specimen, analogous to Figure 3. In general, a significant reduction of compressive strength $\sigma_{c2,max}$ was found for increased transverse tensile strain, analogous to steel reinforced concrete. As expected, more cracks were found at higher tensile strains. For the maximum tensile strains $\varepsilon_{1,max}$ the average panel strains evaluated by DIC are used. Yarn strains were also measured within the test area using FOS, the results of which will be published later. Figure 7 a) shows the maximum compressive strength of the panels $\sigma_{c2,max}$ standardised with $f_{c,cyl}$ for the panels of series 3 and 4 with different maximum tensile strains. Overall, three sections can be assumed within the tests performed, as for example in (Fehling et al., 2008). It can be assumed that there is no change in the compressive strength until transverse cracking is initiated. Subsequently, progressive cracking occurs resulting in the development of smaller concrete lamellae and thus reduced compressive strength. At an average tensile strain of approximately 6 ‰, a complete crack pattern is formed as in uniaxial tensile tests on CRC specimens. Since specimen 4-4 ($\varepsilon_{1,max} = 6 \text{ ‰}$) had a premature anchorage failure, the maximum compressive strength was not reached in this test. It can be assumed that otherwise a compressive strength in the range of specimen 4-3 with $\varepsilon_{1,max} = 5.3 \text{ ‰}$ would have been achieved,

resulting in a lower limit of strength reduction. However, further tests with higher tensile strains are required to confirm these assumptions.

Figure 7: Compressive strength of panels for different maximum transverse tensile strains (a) and stress-strain curves for different tensile strains (b)

Figure 7 b) shows the influence of transverse tension on the stress-strain diagrams of the reinforced specimens from series 4, except for the specimen with premature anchorage failure because the maximum strength was not reached. For comparison, the results of a test from series 3 without transverse loading are also shown. The strains were calculated using the vertical LVDTs. The effect of compression softening can be found in the CRC specimens analogous to steel reinforced concrete. Besides the reduced compressive strength, the compressive stiffness is also reduced with increasing transverse tension.

CONCLUSION

CRC components provide an excellent solution for the realization of sustainable structures with minimized use of materials. For these thin-walled specimens, it is necessary to characterise the behaviour under combined compression and transverse tension, since a reduction of compressive strength occurs. Based on a literature review regarding the characterisation of the compression softening behaviour in steel reinforced concrete, a new test setup was developed for the investigation of CRC panels under uniaxial compression or biaxial compression-tension loading with refined measurement techniques. In contrast to the biaxial loading test setups in literature, brush bearing platens were used for the application of compression loading, resulting in a reduced uniaxial compressive strength compared to panels loaded with conventional steel platens and a significantly different fracture pattern due to the reduced lateral restraint. In addition, the presence of the CFRP yarns, which are sensitive to lateral pressure, resulted in a further reduction of compressive strength. In the first test series with biaxial compression-tension, the reduction of the compressive capacity due to transverse tension was confirmed for CRC depending on the tensile crack state of the specimens. This compression softening behaviour was also observed in the stress-strain diagrams of the specimens under biaxial loading. Further test series with different reinforcement ratios and concrete covers as well as complementary tests with different maximum transverse tensile strains will be carried out in the future to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the compressive behaviour of carbon reinforced concrete subjected to biaxial compression-tension loading and to fully understand the mechanisms leading to the strength reduction. Based on the investigations, refined models for predicting the reduction in compressive strength will be proposed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation)–SFB/TRR 280. Projekt-ID: 417002380. The authors would like to thank the DFG for supporting the research project.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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